

European Public Local Authorities' Network for
driving the Energy Transition

D2.5 - Report on Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) and existing Energy Transition plans & measures databases in the pilot territories

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Executive Summary

ePLANET project is a Coordination and Support Action cofounded by the European Commission through Horizon 2020. ePLANET project aims to deploy new clustering governance for an energy transition based on a digital framework to share harmonised information, facilitating the adoption of coordinated energy transition actions by the European public sector.

This deliverable will set the procedure and key performance indicators (KPIs) for the follow-up and monitoring of the Energy Transition (ET) progress to be used in WP6. In the case of KPIs related to the stakeholder's engagement, data standardisation, data sharing and wider replication, the starting point will be the KPIs defined in line with the ePLANET objectives. In the case of the KPIs related to Green House Gases (GHG) reduction, Renewable Energy Systems (RES) generation increase, and triggered investments, the KPIs will be revised based on the specific pilot site use cases, which have been defined in previous deliverables.

This deliverable will also define the methodology to monitor the impacts. The starting point of this methodology will be a detailed report on KPIs, energy savings achieved by past SEAPS/SECAPs and existing ET plans & measures databases in the pilot territories.

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Abbreviations and acronyms

ABBREVIATION OR ACRONYM	DESCRIPTION
CDD	Cooling Degree Days
EI	Expected Impact
ESCO	Energy Service Company
ET	Energy Transition
ETM	Energy Transition Measures
EU	European Union
GA	Grant agreement
GDP	Gross domestic product
GHG	Greenhouse Gas
HDD	Heating Degree Days
IEA	International Energy Agency
FEC	Final Energy Consumption
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
LA	Local Authority
MoA	Memorandum of Adhesion
PA	Public Authority
PEC	Primary Energy Consumption
PO	Public Officers
PPA	Participant Public Authority
PV	Photovoltaics
RA	Regional Authority
REP	Renewable Energy Production
RES	Renewable Energy Systems / Source
SECAP	Sustainable Energy and Climate Action Plan
UC	Use Case
WP	Work Package

1 Introduction to the ePLANET project

The ePLANET project is a Coordination and Support Action cofunded by the European Commission through Horizon 2020 program. This project aims to deploy **new clustering governance** for an energy transition based on a digital framework to share harmonised information, facilitating the adoption of coordinated energy transition actions by the European public sector.

The development of ePLANET aims at deploying Energy Transition (ET) in the public sector. The main challenges are:

- Improving coordination between local authorities and regional governments,
- Enhancing the decision-making process in the deployment of ET projects,
- Providing coherence and consistency to the energy transition measures (ETM) to be implemented,
- Encouraging the digitalisation of measures and plans,
- Enabling an interoperable ecosystem of data and tools.

These targeted objectives will support the energy transition decision-making process and its practical implementation.

2 Revision of the ePLANET KPIs

2.1 Summary of KPIs defined in the Grant Agreement

The initial general hypotheses which support the ePLANET KPIs are listed below:

- Historical data and statistics at the national level have been taken from the EUROSTAT databases¹. For all calculations, the year 2015 is taken as the last reference year to ensure that the values presented are consolidated.
- The data from intra-national regions, for which reliable historical and statistical data were unavailable, have been extrapolated from national data. It was assumed that the contribution of the specific region would be proportional to the percentage of national GDP it represents (Crete region 4.9% of Greece's GDP; Girona province 1.85% of Spain's GDP; Zlín region 4.75% for Czech Rep; Catalonia region 19.06% of Spain GDP).
- The estimation of impacts over time is calculated in different phases. These phases are related to the forecast implementation of the ePLANET methodology over time, as specified in the project work plan. The phases that are considered are the following:
 - **Phase 1 (Testing and pilot deployment):** During the first year of the project, the project will be deployed in the three pilot/test regions (CRETE, GIRONA, and ZLÍN). The primary considerations and hypotheses for estimating different impacts in these regions will be provided by pilot leaders' partners and their contrasted experience (RDFC, DDGI, EAZK).
 - **Phase 2 (Transferring and expansion):**
 - **Scaling up regions:** The ePLANET consortium expects a smooth project replication in the upper administrative levels of pilot regions (GREECE, CATALONIA and CZECH REPUBLIC).
 - **Implementation in other EU regions:** Through the "open call" process, the ePLANET consortium aims at including 6 additional European regions in the project (see WP5).

Table 2-1 summarises the KPIs defined in the ePLANET Grant Agreement. Each KPI is named Expected Impact (EI) and numbered correspondingly.

¹ Eurostat Data Base: <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/web/sdi/main-tables>

Table 2-1. Summary of the KPIs of the ePLANET project

Impact Indicator	Description	Unit	Within the project	Phase 1- Testing and pilot deployment	Phase 2- Transferring and expansion
EI-1	Number of active stakeholders	Stakeholder	764	144 (local) + 6 (regional)	427 (local) + 37 (regional) + 150 (other)
EI-2	Number of institutionalized collaborations on ETM among PA	PPA	603	144 (local) + 3 (regional)	427 (local) + 29 (regional)
EI-3	Number of PA and PO with improved skills in Energy Transition	PPA	904	-----	904
EI-4	Number of policies influenced	Policies	32	-----	32
EI-5	PEC savings triggered	GWh/year	177.60	34.79 (5 % reduction PEC/year)	142.81 (1 % reduction PEC/year)
EI-6	REP triggered	GWh/year	12.26	2.63 (5 % increase REC/year)	9.63 (5 % increase REC/year)
EI-7	Investments in sustainable energy triggered	million EUR	85	-----	85 (0.5 % of overall investments)

2.2 EI-1 Number of active stakeholders in delivering ET

The main ePLANET stakeholders will be:

- Local authorities
- Regional authorities
- Energy agencies
- Energy Transition facilitators (Urban planners, sustainability and Energy experts, ESCOs, investors and industry stakeholders).

To reach all these target groups, ePLANET carries out many communication, dissemination, training and capacity-building actions. These actions are summarized in the following objective: 24 capacity building activities (8 by pilot), 3 site visits and 12 meetings of stakeholders' forums (4 per year).

2.2.1 The hypotheses defined in the grant agreement

2.2.1.1 *Phase 1: Testing and pilot deployment*

This EI is focused on PA stakeholders. That means technicians and decision makers belonging to a PA. Therefore, the figures defined in the EI-1 of Table 2-1 are split among the different pilot sites, as summarised in Table 2-2.

Table 2-2. Number of active PA (persons) in each pilot site from the GA

Administrative level	Crete Island	Girona Province	Zlín region	TOTAL
Local authorities	16	67	61	144
Regional authorities	2	2	2	6

2.2.1.2 Phase 2: Transferring and expansion

The ePLANET replication will be made in two steps: i) scaling up over pilot regions; ii) and implementing the project in other EU regions. This second phase also aims at engaging other stakeholders beyond the PA. The hypotheses to sustain this KPI in this project stage are summarised below:

- The number of Local Authorities (LA) of the upper administrative levels capable of being active in ePLANET is defined by considering 20 % of all the municipalities of each upper level (Greece, Catalonia and Czech Republic) but excluding the pilot site regions. However, since the number of municipalities was too big in the Czech Republic, this percentage was reduced to 2 %.
- The number of Regional Authorities (RA) of the upper administrative levels capable of being involved in ePLANET is defined as 1.5 RA per region. In the Czech Republic, the number is limited to 10.
- The number of PAs from other EU regions capable of being involved in ePLANET is obtained by assuming that 6 new EU regions will be involved in the project. Therefore, the overall figure estimates 17 municipalities per region and 17 regional authorities among these new EU regions.
- The number of other stakeholders beyond PA is assumed as 150, which will be engaged through the stakeholders' forums.

The following tables summarise the specific figures for each stakeholder category and administrative level.

Table 2-3. Number of potential active PA (persons) in the upper level of each pilot site from the GA

Administrative level	Greece	Catalonia	Czech Republic	TOTAL
Local Authorities (LA)	62 (20% of 308)	145 (20% of 725)	119 (2% of 5951)	326
Regional Authorities (RA)	9 (12 regions)	6 (4 regions)	10 (14 regions)	25

Table 2-4. Number of potential active PA (persons) in other EU regions from the GA

Other EU regions	Number of regions	N° of LA per region	TOTAL
Local Authorities (LA)	6	17	101
Regional authorities (RA)	6	-----	17

2.2.2 Revision of the KPIs pilot site-by-pilot site basis

2.2.2.1 Girona province pilot site and Catalonia Region

The KPIs of this pilot site don't change in relation to those identified in Table 2-2 and Table 2-3. They are summarized as follows:

Phase 1 (number of persons)	
Administrative level	Girona province
Local authorities	67
Regional authorities	2
Phase 2 (number of persons)	
Administrative level	Catalonia
Local authorities	145
Regional authorities	6

2.2.2.2 Zlín region pilot site and the Czech Republic

The KPIs of this pilot site change in relation to phase 2 since the administrative organization and the number of regions within the category of NUTS3² of the Czech Republic is 14. Therefore, the objective of engaging ten regions is considered not realistic. Thus, the concept of "region" will be extended to any kind of association of municipalities. This makes the following changes in relation to the KPIs identified in Table 2-2 and Table 2-3. They are summarized as follows:

Phase 1	
Administrative level	Zlín Region
Local authorities	61
Regional authorities	2
Phase 2	
Administrative level	Czech Republic
Local authorities	119
Regional/municipal association authorities	10

2.2.2.3 Crete Island pilot site and Greece

The KPIs of this pilot site don't change in relation to those identified in Table 2-2 and Table 2-3. They are summarized as follows:

Phase 1	
Administrative level	Crete Island
Local authorities	16
Regional authorities	2

² Eurostat NUTS classification: Nomenclature of territorial units for statistics
<https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/web/nuts/background>

Phase 2	
Administrative level	Greece
Local authorities	62
Regional authorities	9

2.3 EI-2 Number of institutionalized collaborations on ETM among PA

2.3.1 The hypotheses defined in the grant agreement

The ePLANET project will institutionalise the collaboration on the energy transition between public authorities by signing a Memorandum of Adhesion (MoA) by each public authority involved in the project. The way these PA will be engaged through the following actions:

- 6 private capacity building activities by pilot site (4 webinars and 2 workshops).
- 2 public activities in Crete, Zlín region and Girona province

2.3.1.1 Phase 1: Testing and pilot deployment

The project is committed to institutionalizing collaboration with the following regional public authorities, as summarised in Table 2-5.

Table 2-5. Number of institutionalizing collaborative PPA in each pilot site from the GA

Administrative level	Crete Island	Girona Province	Zlín region	TOTAL
Local authorities	16	67	61	144
Regional authorities	1	1	1	3

2.3.1.2 Phase 2: Transferring and expansion

In the project replication phase, it is expected to implement the project at the national level in participating territories and other regions of the EU. In this phase, the project hopes to achieve the following institutionalised collaborations.

Table 2-6. Number of collaborative PPA in the upper level of each pilot site from the GA

Administrative level	Crete Island	Girona Province	Zlín region	TOTAL
Local authorities	60	145	119	326
Regional authorities	6	14	7	17

Table 2-7. Number of potential collaborative PA in other EU Regions from the GA

Administrative level	Number of regions	N° of PA per region	TOTAL
Local authorities	6	17	101
Regional authorities	6	-----	12

2.3.2 Revision of the KPIs pilot site-by-pilot site basis

The main objectives of the KPIs are the same as in the previous section, 2.3.1. Therefore, no modifications are added.

2.4 EI-3 Number of PA and PO with improved skills in Energy Transition

2.4.1 The hypotheses defined in the grant agreement

The direct influence of the ePLANET project will reach many public authorities and officers who will have access to the ePLANET platform and to all the training and capacity-building material that will be generated in the project. From the knowledge of the management and organization of the public officers that some of our project partners have (DIGI, RDFC, EAZK, ICAEN and CRES), it is estimated that in additionally to PPA with MoA signed, the project can involve another 50% of PPA's.

Therefore, it is expected that ePLANET will improve the capacity and skills in delivering Energy Transition to 904 public officers and public authorities.

2.4.2 Revision of the KPIs pilot site-by-pilot site basis

Since the grant agreement does not define the distribution of this KPI among the three pilot sites, it is made based on the number of involved municipalities of each pilot site in phase 2 of the project (see Table 2-3). Therefore, the KPI of PA and PO with improved skills in delivering energy transition will be:

Table 2-8. Number of PA and PO with improved skills per pilot site from the GA

Stakeholders	Crete Island/Greece	Girona Province/Catalonia	Zlín region/Czech republic	TOTAL
PO and PA	172	402	330	904

2.5 EI-4 Number of policies influenced

2.5.1 The hypotheses defined in the grant agreement

Regarding the energy transition policies, the public administrations that can develop or implement them are those at the regional, national or state levels. Therefore, the ePLANET project envisages institutionalizing collaboration with at least 32 regional administrations.

The number of policies influenced through the ePLANET actions will be higher than 32.

2.5.2 Revision of the KPIs pilot site-by-pilot site basis

Since the grant agreement does not define the distribution of this KPI among the three pilot sites, it will be made based on the number of involved regions/countries of each pilot site. Therefore, the number of policies to be influenced by ePLANET will be:

Table 2-9 Number of policies influenced per pilot site from the GA

Stakeholders	Crete Island/ Greece	Girona Province/ Catalonia	Zlín region/ Czech republic	TOTAL
Number of policies	12	13	7	32

2.6 EI-5 Primary energy savings triggered by the project

2.6.1 The hypotheses defined in the grant agreement

The reduction targets in the 2030 horizon set by Europe directly influence the reduction of Primary Energy Consumption (PEC) triggered by the ePLANET project. Energy efficiency can be accelerated by digitalization and improved governance with respect to the trend in the last two decades, as was pointed out in the article “Energy efficiency and digitalisation” by the International Energy Agency (IEA). Based on the consortium’s experience, it could be accelerated up to 30%. The use of tools and actions of the project will accelerate the achievements of PEC reduction. However, the enrolment time will directly affect the effect in the selected regions, for this is discretized into two phases:

- Phase 1 (3 pilots, project partners) will accelerate the reduction of the PEC to be achieved in 2030 (1,129 % per year) by 5% of this amount.
- Phase 2 (replication) in the 7 additional regions that are reached through the "open call", the PEC reduction will be accelerated by 2.5% of the expected PEC to be achieved until 2030. In the scaling-up regions, inside the administrative regions, and upper to 3 pilot regions project partners, the project hopes to accelerate, at least, by 1% of the expected PEC reduction.

2.6.1.1 Phase 1: Testing and pilot deployment

The following table presents the estimated PEC for the reference year (2015), for the 2030 goals, and the PEC to be triggered by the project. This table comes from the GA. First, the figures of the PEC 2015 and PEC 2030 of each pilot site have been obtained by multiplying the PEC of each country by the percentage of the GDP that each pilot area represents in relation to the overall GDP of the corresponding country (see initial impact hypothesis of section 2.1). Then, the reduction by year is calculated as the subtraction of the PEC 2030 and the PEC 2015 divided by the period (15 years). Once the yearly reduction is determined, the PEC triggered by the project is 5 % of this annual reduction applied for the operation period, which will be 1 year.

Table 2-10 Estimated PEC savings to be triggered in the pilot sites from the GA

Phase 1 (testing and deployment)	Crete Island	Girona Province	Zlín region	TOTAL	Units
PEC2015	12,742.46	25,585.98	23,795	62,123.30	GWh
PEC2030	10,601.72	21287.54	19,797	51,686.59	GWh
Reduction by year	142.72	285.56	267	695.78	GWh/y
Triggered by the project (5%)	7.14	14.33	13	34.79	GWh/y

Besides the figures of PEC from Table 2-10, in the GA, there is also an estimation of the FEC of the pilot site regions (it is found on page 27). The figures of the FEC for the reference year (2015) and 2030 are summarized below:

Table 2-11 Estimated FEC savings triggered by the project on the pilot regions from the GA

Phase 1 (testing and deploy)	Crete Island	Girona Province	Zlín region	TOTAL	Units
PEC2015 (FEC)	1,484	2,783	2,115	6,382	GWh
PEC2030 (FEC)	1,293	2,424	1,842	5,559	GWh
Reduction by year	12.73	24.93	18.2	54.8	GWh/y
Triggered by the project (5%)	0.64	1.19	0.91	2.74	GWh/y

A comparison between Table 2-10 and Table 2-11 shows some inconsistencies in the hypothesis defined in the GA. For instance, in the case of Girona province, the PEC figures, in both 2015 and 2030, are 9 times bigger than the FEC for the same years. That means the overall primary energy factor for Spain is about 9. This value is entirely out of scope. Approximated estimates for Spain's primary and final energy consumption in 2019, made by the European Energy Agency³, show an overall PEC/FEC = 1.4. Therefore, these figures will be revised and harmonized with the reality of the pilot site regions in section 2.6.2.

2.6.1.2 Phase 2: Transferring and expansion

In the GA, it is stated that in the project replication phase, it is expected to implement the project at the national level in pilot territories and other regions of the EU. The expected PEC savings defined in the GA are summarized below:

1. Implementation in the upper administration level of each pilot region (Greece, Catalonia and the Czech Republic): Taken into account the transposition of the EU targets by 2030 in these upper administrative levels (excluding the pilots) and assuming conservatively that the project will accelerate these savings by 1%, the following numbers are presented in the table below. The specific figures of PEC of the reference year, as well as the ones for the 2030 objectives, are deducted from the IEA World Energy balances (2019)⁴:

Table 2-12 Estimated PEC savings to be triggered in the upper administration level of the pilot regions from the GA

Phase 1 (testing and deploy)	Greece	Catalonia	Czech Rep.	TOTAL	Units
PEC2015	247,308	238,050	477,150	962,507	GWh
PEC2030	205,760	198,058	396,989	800,806	GWh
Reduction by year	2,770	2,666	5,344	10,780	GWh/y
Triggered by the project (1%)	28	27	53	108	GWh/y

Besides the figures of PEC from Table 2-12, in the GA, there is also an estimation of the FEC (it is found on page 27). The figures of the FEC for the reference year (2015) and 2030 are summarized below:

³ <https://www.eea.europa.eu/data-and-maps/data/approximated-estimates-for-the-primary-4>

⁴ <https://www.iea.org/subscribe-to-data-services/world-energy-balances-and-statistics>

Table 2-13 Estimated FEC savings triggered by the project on pilot upper administrative level from the GA

Phase 1 (testing and deploy)	Greece	Catalonia	Czech Rep.	TOTAL	Units
PEC2015 (FEC)	28,808	25,890	42,410	97,108	GWh
PEC2030 (FEC)	25,092	22,550	36,939	84,581	GWh
Reduction by year	247.73	222.66	364.73	835.13	GWh/y
Triggered by the project (1%)	2.47	2.22	3.64	8.35	GWh/y

A comparison between Table 2-12 and Table 2-13 shows some inconsistencies in the hypothesis defined in the GA. For instance, in the case of Catalonia, the PEC in both 2015 and 2030 is around 9 times bigger than the FEC for the same years. That means the primary energy factor for Spain is about 9. This value is entirely out of scope. Approximated estimates for Spain's primary and final energy consumption in 2019, made by the European Energy Agency⁵, show an overall PEC/FEC = 1.4. Therefore, these figures will be revised and harmonized with the reality of the pilot site regions in section 2.6.2.

2. Implementation in other EU regions: As defined in the GA, the project replication work package (see WP5) is expected to include at least 6 other European regions through an open call. In these 6 regions, the reduction of PEC to be triggered by the ePLANET project (assuming these regions will be similar in magnitude to the 3 pilot partner regions) will be at least 50 % of the impact achieved in the partner regions. Therefore, we can consider that the reduction of PEC in these 6 new regions will be accelerated by 2.5% with respect to the initial forecasts. (pilot average: $34,8/3 \text{ GWh/y} = 11,6 \text{ GWh/y}$, 50% factor $\rightarrow 5,8 \text{ GWh/y}$ by new region). The reduction of PEC to be triggered by the project in these 6 regions will be: $6 \text{ regions} \times 5,8 \text{ GWh/y} = 34,8 \text{ GWh/y}$.

As in the estimations made for phase 1, on page 27 of the GA, there is an estimation of the FEC savings the project can trigger in other EU regions. Suppose we follow the same approach as for the estimated PEC savings. In that case, we can consider that the reduction of FEC in the 6 new EU regions will be accelerated by 2.5 % through the ePLANET (50% less than the pilot regions). The estimation is based on the figures in Table 2-11 since these follower regions will have very similar characteristics to the pilot regions. From Table 2-11, it can be deduced that the expected average FEC savings triggered in the 3 pilot regions is 0.91 GWh/year. Assuming the follower regions can activate 50 % of these FEC savings, the expected average FEC savings per follower region would be 0.45 GWh/year. Considering 6 follower regions, this makes total FEC savings triggered by the project of 2.74 GWh/year.

Suppose we compare the FEC savings and PEC savings. It can be seen that there is a profound inconsistency since the calculated primary energy factor is about 12, which is entirely out of scope. Therefore, as in previous cases, this KPI will be revised.

2.6.2 Revision of the KPIs pilot site-by-pilot site basis

In the previous section, it was stated that there are some inconsistencies in the specific figures of PEC and FEC savings to be triggered by the ePLANET project. Hence, although the estimated percentages are consistent, the figures have a large discrepancy. Furthermore, when we analyse the implementation in the pilot sites, based on the Use Cases (UC) summarized in

⁵ <https://www.eea.europa.eu/data-and-maps/data/approximated-estimates-for-the-primary-4>

deliverable D.2.3, it can be appreciated that the initial hypotheses set out in the Grant Agreement are no longer valid.

From the use cases defined in ePLANET (Deliverable D.2.3), the following ones will be monitored through this EI:

- UC1- Digitalization of SECAP drafting and monitoring process: This use case will be applied to Crete Island and Girona province. More specifically, 16 municipalities of Crete and 67 municipalities of Girona will be involved in this use case.
- UC2- Analysis of the energy performance of the public building stock: This use case will be applied to the Zlín Region and Crete Island public buildings. More specifically, this use case will include around 380 public buildings belonging to 61 municipalities and the regional government of the Zlín region and 450 buildings belonging to the 16 municipalities of the Crete region.

These two use cases will constrain the revision of this EI.

2.6.2.1 *Phase 1: Testing and pilot deployment*

UC1: Digitalization of SECAP drafting and monitoring process.

The definition of the EI-5 sets an annual PEC reduction of 1.129 % in the European regions to achieve the EU 2030 GHG emissions reduction target. From the pilot regions, it is expected that a 5% of this reduction is accelerated due to the ePLANET. These goals are transformed into measurable figures through the SECAP that each pilot site municipality has signed and needs to update within the ePLANET project duration. Each SECAP has as main inputs the SECAP template files, which summarise the inventory of GHG of each municipality. This file doesn't contain the evaluation of the PEC. It is limited to summarizing the FEC and the GHG emissions because these are the KPIs used to evaluate the SECAP in Europe.

Considering these constraints, the EI-5 will be transformed to “EI-5 Final Energy Consumption CO_{2-eq} emissions and Primary Energy Consumption savings triggered by the project”, which is equivalent to the previous definition of PEC savings to be triggered by the project.

The specific figures of FEC, PEC and CO_{2-eq} emissions savings to be achieved within ePLANET in the two pilot site regions (Crete Island and Girona province) will be found following the next steps:

1. To gather data on the submitted SECAP of each municipality from the first release of the MyCovenant platform, published by the JRC⁶
2. To obtain a baseline of FEC and CO_{2-eq} emissions of each municipality from the information provided by each municipality
3. To aggregate the baseline of each municipality at the pilot site level
4. To estimate the FEC and CO_{2-eq} emissions savings by considering a 5 % of the committed savings until 2030
5. Estimate the PEC from the FEC using the available conversion indicators. In the Girona pilot is used the available indicator for Spain proportionated by the Spanish Ministry for

⁶ Baldi, Marta; Tsemekidi tzeiranaki , Sofia; Bertoldi , Paolo; Franco de Los Rios, Camilo; Melica, Giulia ; Treville, Aldo; Clemente, Massimo; kakoulaki, Georgia (2021): GCoM - MyCovenant, 2021, First release. European Commission, Joint Research Centre (JRC) [Dataset] PID: <http://data.europa.eu/89h/86ec3e42-f8e1-4cdb-a953-d396251d2029>

Ecological Transition and the Demographic Challenge⁷ (PEC/FEC=1.39). In the Crete pilot is used the available indicator for Greece proportionated by the Institute of Energy for South-East Europe⁸ (PEC/FEC=1.34).

The data gathered from each SECAP collected data is split by sector, energy carrier and municipality. In addition, the baseline is set for the reference year of each municipality (date of adhesion to the CoM).

Figure 2-1 shows the baseline of the aggregated FEC (MWh) and the CO_{2-eq} emissions (tonnes) of all the involved municipalities belonging to the pilot in Crete Island. Detailed consumption and emissions values of the baseline for each municipality can be found in Annex I.

Figure 2-1. Aggregated FEC and CO_{2-eq} emissions from Crete island based on the reference year of each municipality.

Figure 2-2 shows the baseline of the aggregated FEC (MWh) and the CO_{2-eq} emissions (tonnes) of all the involved municipalities belonging to the pilot in the Girona province. Detailed consumption and emissions values of the baseline for each municipality can be found in Annex I.

⁷ Spanish Ministry for Ecological Transition and the Demographic Challenge: Press release “España cumple los objetivos europeos de renovables y eficiencia energética en 2020”, December 2021: https://www.miteco.gob.es/es/prensa/211227_ndpespanacumplelosobjetivos europeosderenovablesyeficienciaenergeticaen2020_tcm30-534574.pdf

⁸ Theofylaktos, Costas: South East Europe Energy Outlook 2021/2022, March 2022: https://www.iene.eu/articlefiles/inline/iene_see%20outlook_010322_athens_theofylactos.pdf

Figure 2-2. Aggregated FEC and CO_{2-eq} emissions from Girona province based on the reference year of each municipality.

The expected FEC and CO_{2-eq} savings are defined in the SECAP of each municipality. However, since the date of submissions is not the same, and the updates of the JRC don't include the last SECAP updates submitted, the FEC and CO_{2-eq} will be based on the commitments of each country, Spain and Greece. Therefore, the FEC and CO_{2-eq} will be calculated as the product between the baseline (see Figure 2-1 and Figure 2-2), the country-based commitments, the committed 5 % (see GA), and the percentage to be triggered by the ePLANET project along its duration.

Table 2-14 Use case 1: revised FEC savings and CO_{2-eq} emissions reduction to be triggered by ePLANET in the involved pilot site regions

	FEC Savings	CO _{2-eq}		
Baseline Girona	5,600,179 MWh	1,808,869 tCO _{2-eq}		
Baseline Crete	5,662,068 MWh	2,510,549 tCO _{2-eq}		
	Objectives 2030 (9 years)		ePLANET-2024 (3 years)	
	FEC Savings	CO _{2-eq} emissions reduction	FEC Savings	CO _{2-eq} emissions reduction
Spain	36%	55%	5%	5%
Girona province (67 municipalities)	2,016,064.44 MWh	994,877.95 tCO _{2-eq}	33,601.07 MWh	16,581.30 tCO _{2-eq}
Greece	32.5%	40%	5%	5%
Crete Island (16 municipalities)	1,840,172.10 MWh	1,004,219.60 tCO _{2-eq}	30,669.54 MWh	16,736.99 tCO _{2-eq}
TOTAL PHASE 1-USE CASE 1			64,270.61 MWh	33,318.29 tCO_{2-eq}

In Table 2-15 is presented the FEC and PEC ePLANET reduction target for the use case 1 in the involved pilot regions.

Table 2-15 Use case 1: revised FEC and PEC triggered by ePLANET in the involved pilot site regions

	ePLANET FEC (3 years)	ePLANET PEC (3 years)
Girona province (67 municipalities)	33,601.07 MWh	46,705.49 MWh
Crete Island (16 municipalities)	30,669.54 MWh	41,097.18 MWh
TOTAL PHASE 1-USE CASE 1	64,270.61 MWh	87,802.67 MWh

UC2: Analysis of the energy performance of the public building stock

To translate the objectives of the EI-5 to this use case, we can't use exact figures since there is no historical data available on the energy consumption of the public buildings from the Zlín region and Crete Island. Therefore, we will define a relative percentage of FEC, PEC and CO_{2-eq} emissions reduction as the KPI to be achieved. Based on previous experiences, it is realistic to assume the following figures:

- Crete Island: To assume a 5 % reduction of FEC, 5 % reduction of PEC and a 5 % reduction of CO_{2-eq} emissions
- Zlín region: To assume a 5 % reduction of FEC, 5 % reduction of PEC and a 5 % reduction of CO_{2-eq} emissions

To assess the objective of energy and GHG emissions reduction, we need to consider that the analysis of the energy performance of buildings should include the influence of external factors like the weather. Comparing a building's consumption only with itself over the years without considering the external operating conditions will have a considerable bias. As climatization has a relevant contribution to the energy consumption in buildings, the weather conditions affect the building's energy demand. Therefore, the evolution of building energy consumption in different time stages should be performed under the same conditions. As having the same building under the same conditions is practically impossible, it should be done by modelling techniques applied to the building's energy performance.

Training and validating a building model allow for capturing the behaviour of the building on the data period used. Therefore, a building energy performance model should be created to compare the building in different periods. This model is called "baseline" and will help to predict the expected energy consumption of a specific building if no investment in energy efficiency is implemented (Business as Usual situation). The FEC savings once the ePLANET platform is running and the ETM are applied is then determined as the difference between this baseline energy consumption" and the measured energy consumed for the specific period, in this case, the second phase of the ePLANET project.

In ePLANET, data-driven modelling techniques will be used to model the baseline energy consumption as a function of the external weather conditions and other input variables related to the expected building occupancy (hour of the day, day of the week...). The baseline consumption depends on the use of the building. Normally this consumption can be discretized in 3 different user behaviours, one corresponding to a weekday, another to the weekends and finally, one for the holidays. The climatization energy consumption is modelled by determining the Cooling Degree Days (CDD) and the Heating Degree Days (HDD). The CDD is the amount of time (hours) when the exterior temperature is higher than the indoor setpoint temperature multiplied by the temperature difference. This is a widely used parameter which indirectly

indicates the required cooling need in a specified period. The HDD is the same concept as the CDD; however, considering the time the external temperature is below the temperature setpoint.

The building energy consumption model to be used as the baseline model in this use case will follow the following equation:

$$Q_{e,t} = \beta_{wd}N_{wd,t} + \beta_{we}N_{we,t} + \beta_{wh}N_{wh,t} + \beta_{HDD}HDD_t + \beta_{CDD}CDD_t + \varepsilon_t$$

Where:

$Q_{e,t}$: monthly electricity or gas consumption [kWh]

$\beta_{wd}, \beta_{we}, \beta_{wh}, \beta_{HDD}, \beta_{CDD}$: Unknown coefficients to be identified

$N_{wd,t}$: number of the day within the week

$N_{we,t}$: number of the week within the year

$N_{wh,t}$: number of the hour within the day

HDD_t : number of heating degree days in a month

CDD_t : number of cooling degree days in a month

ε_t : statistical error of the model

To train the baseline building energy model, two possible modelling techniques will be assessed:

- Least square linear model with auto-regressive terms
- Recursive least square model.

The linear model is the simplest one. It is trained period by period separately to get the different models to compare. Conversely, the recursive least square is a more complex model technique. This technique makes a model that self-trains in each iteration. In this way, the model evolves in each iteration. While the model is getting new data, it also forgets old data to better adapt it to building response changes. Avoiding the data split and having a continuous adaptable model could better detect the period when the building response changes.

2.6.2.2 Phase 2: Transferring and expansion

UC1: Digitalization of SECAP drafting and monitoring process.

In phase 2, this use case will consist in involving other follower regions from the open call of WP5 (7 already selected) and from the regions or municipalities which sign the Memorandum of Adhesion within the upper level of the two involved pilot sites. Following the figures defined in the EI-1, the potential number of regions/municipalities to be engaged are:

- Upper level:
 - Catalonia: 6 regions/counties
 - Greece: 9 regions
- Other EU regions:
 - Follower regions: 7

Only the percentage established in the GA is valid to assess the potential FEC, PEC and GHG emissions reduction. It corresponds to the 1% of the FEC, PEC and CO_{2-eq} emissions reduction

committed by each newly engaged region by 2030. This percentage is translated into specific figures by estimating a generic region of the Girona Province in Catalonia is considered. Since there are only 3 more provinces equivalent to Girona province in Catalonia, the concept of “region” will be translated to “county”. The 67 municipalities of Girona province are equivalent to 2 counties from the 7 counties of the whole province; therefore, the generic region will have a baseline of FEC, PEC and CO_{2-eq} equivalent to 2/7 the figures of the Girona Province. In the case of Greece, Crete Island includes 4 regional units. The regional units have no administrative structure; however, as this was unknown when the GA was written, they are considered a group of municipalities to measure the Greek engagement. Therefore, the following approach will be followed:

1. To use the aggregated FEC and CO_{2-eq} emissions reduction of 1/4 of Crete Island and 2/7 of the Girona province, from Table 2-14, as the baseline.
2. To estimate the FEC and CO_{2-eq} emissions savings at the upper level (Greece and Catalonia) by considering a 1 % of the baseline.
3. To estimate the FEC and CO_{2-eq} emissions savings of a European follower region by considering an average between the committed savings of Girona province and Crete Island.
4. To evaluate the overall number of expected FEC and CO_{2-eq} emissions savings by considering 7 follower EU regions, 6 counties in Girona and 9 regions in Greece.
5. Estimate the PEC from the FEC using the available conversion indicators like in the first phase PEC estimation. For the PEC estimation in the follower regions is used the available indicator for Europe⁹ (PEC/FEC=1.36).

Table 2-16 shows the results of the revised figures for this use case.

⁹ IEA: Primary and final energy consumption in the European Union, October 2022: https://www.eea.europa.eu/data-and-maps/daviz/primary-and-final-energy-consumption-7#tab-googlechartid_chart_41

Table 2-16 Phase 2: Use case 1: revised FEC savings and CO_{2-eq} emissions reduction to be triggered by ePLANET in the upper level and other EU regions

	FEC	CO _{2-eq} emissions		
Baseline Girona	5,600,179 MWh	1,808,869 tCO _{2-eq}		
Baseline Crete	5,662,068 MWh	2,510,549 tCO _{2-eq}		
Average	5,631,123.50 MWh	2,159,709 tCO _{2-eq}		
	Objectives 2030 (9 years)		ePLANET-2024 (3 years)	
	FEC Savings (MWh)	CO _{2-eq} emissions reduction (tCO _{2-eq})	FEC Savings (MWh)	CO _{2-eq} emissions reduction (tCO _{2-eq})
Spain	36%	55%		
Girona province (67 municipalities)	2,016,064.44 MWh	994,877.95 tCO _{2-eq}		
Generic region (county)	2/7 by 1 %	2/7 by 1 %	1,920.06 MWh	947.50 tCO _{2-eq}
Total Catalonia	6 counties	6 counties	11,520.37 MWh	5,685.02 tCO _{2-eq}
Greece	32.5%	40%		
Crete Island (16 municipalities)	1,840,172.10 MWh	1,004,219.60 tCO _{2-eq}		
Generic region	1%	1%	1,533.48 MWh	836.85 tCO _{2-eq}
Total Greece	9 regions	9 regions	13,801.29 MWh	7,531.65 tCO _{2-eq}
Other EU Regions	30%	55%		
Average	1,689,337.05 MWh	1,187,839.95 tCO _{2-eq}		
Generic follower region	1%	1%	5,631.12 MWh	3,959.47 tCO _{2-eq}
Total follower regions	7 regions/counties	7 regions/counties	39,417.86 MWh	27,716.27 tCO _{2-eq}
TOTAL PHASE 2-USE CASE 1			64,739.52 MWh	40,932.93 tCO_{2-eq}

In Table 2-17 is presented the FEC and PEC ePLANET reduction target for the use case 2.

Table 2-17 Phase 2: Use case 1: revised FEC and PEC triggered by ePLANET

	ePLANET FEC (3 years)	ePLANET PEC (3 years)
Catalonia	11,520.37 MWh	16,013.31 MWh
Greece	13,801.29 MWh	18,493.73 MWh
Follower regions	39,417.86 MWh	53,629.16 MWh
TOTAL PHASE 2-USE CASE 1	64,739.52 MWh	88,136.20 MWh

UC2: Analysis of the energy performance of the public building stock

As in the case of phase 1, the triggered savings in FEC and CO_{2-eq} emissions will be assessed by developing a specific building energy performance model for the public buildings to be provided by the engaged municipalities in the upper level of the pilot sites and the follower regions.

Furthermore, we will define a relative percentage of FEC and CO_{2-eq} emissions reduction as the KPI to be achieved. Based on previous experiences, it is realistic to assume the following figures:

- Greece: To consider a 2.5 % reduction of FEC and a 2.5 % reduction of CO₂-eq emissions.
- Czech Republic: To consider a 2.5 % reduction of FEC and a 2.5 % reduction of CO₂-eq emissions.
- Other EU regions: To consider a 1 % reduction of FEC and 1 % of CO₂-eq emissions.

2.7 EI-6 Renewable energy production triggered by the project

2.7.1 The hypotheses defined in the grant agreement

Accelerating the achievements of the EU targets related to Renewable Energy Production (REP) is an objective of the ePLANET project. The ePLANET will contribute to this achievement by supporting public authorities in the planning, execution, monitoring and verification of the renewable energy implementation. The EI-6 has the same time effect as the EI-5, so it's discretized in the same way:

- Phase 1 (Testing and pilot deployment) will accelerate the REP by 5%.
- Phase 2 (Transferring and expansion) in the 7 additional regions reached through the "open call" will accelerate the REP by 2.5%. In the scaling-up regions, inside the administrative regions upper to 3 pilots regions project partners, the project expects to accelerate, at least, by 1% the REP.

2.7.1.1 *Phase 1: Testing and pilot deployment*

In the first project phase, the REP triggered by ePLANET will be done in the project regions. Therefore, it is expected that the ePLANET project will accelerate a 5% of the REP needed to accomplish the EU target of 32% of REP.

Table 2-18 Estimation of the REP triggered by the project on the pilot regions

Phase 1 (testing and deploy)	Crete Island		Girona Province		Zlín region		TOTAL	Units
	FEC	REP	FEC	REP	FEC	REP		
PEC2015	1484	(15.69%) 233	2783	(16.23%) 452	2115	(15.07%) 319	1004	GWh
PEC2030	1293	(32%) 414	2424	(32%) 776	1842	(32%) 589	1779	GWh
Increase od REC by year		12.1		21.6		18	51.7	GWh/y
Triggered by the project (5%)		0.6		1.1		0.9	2.6	GWh/y

2.7.1.2 *Phase 2: Transferring and expansion*

In phase 2 of the project, the scale-up regions will beneficiate from the ePLANET outcomes. Project replications in nearby territories (upper administrative level) (Greece, Catalonia, Czech Republic) are considered to accelerate the implementation of REP by 1% (excluding the pilots).

Table 2-19 Estimation of the REP triggered by the project on the pilot upper administrative level

Phase 2 (transfer and replication)	Greece		Catalunya		Czech Republic		TOTAL	Units
	FEC	REP	FEC	REP	FEC	REP		
PEC2015	28808	(15.69%) 4520	25890	(16.23%) 4062	42410	(15.07%) 6654	16240	GWh
PEC2030	25092	(32%) 8029	22550	(32%) 7216	36939	(32%) 11821	28845	GWh
Increase of REP by year		233.96		210.26		344.43	788.65	GWh/y
Triggered by the project (1%)		2.34		2.10		3.44	7.88	GWh/y

In the 6 regions which will enrol with the ePLANET project, it is expected that the project will accelerate the implementation of REP by 2.5%. Assuming that the average final energy consumption from these regions is the same as the pilot regions, the expected REP triggered by the project is 2.6 GWh/y.

2.7.2 Revision of the KPIs pilot site-by-pilot site basis

From the previous section, it can be deduced that the percentage of increase in REP is coherent with the specific conditions of the pilot sites. However, the overall figures are based on some general hypotheses which are no longer valid. Therefore, to transform the figures defined in the GA into specific figures capable of being tracked, the framework will be the SECAP that each pilot site municipality has signed and need to update within the ePLANET project duration.

2.7.2.1 Phase 1: Testing and pilot deployment

Each SECAP has as main inputs the SECAP template files, which summarise the inventory of GHG of each municipality. In addition, this file includes a more detailed figure of the REP of each municipality for a reference year.

The following figure shows the REP of the reference year obtained from the SECAPs for the pilot in Crete Island. Detailed RES generation and source for each municipality can be found in Annex I. The reference year is assumed the year 2012. As can be seen in Figure 2-3, the overall REP for 2012 was 74.219 MWh/year.

Figure 2-3 Total REP of the reference year for all the municipalities belonging to the Crete island pilot site

The figures in Figure 2-3 are not entirely consistent with other data sources of RES installed in Crete. There are some authors, such as A. Gigantidou¹⁰ and J.Vourdoubas¹¹, which accounts for more RES power installed on the island. They documented RES power in 2018 of around 80 MW of PV parks, 15 MW of solar PV rooftop systems and 200 MW of Wind parks. Therefore, from Figure 2-3, we will only consider the REP due to PV systems as the baseline. This figure is very similar to the PV installations placed on rooftops documented by the previous authors. These are the kind of RES that will benefit most from the actions to be considered within the ePLANET project.

To determine the annual REP triggered by the project, a figure of the REP of a more recent year should be found. The equivalent figure of this kind of PV installation for a closer year, 2019, has been provided by RDFC. In 2019, the installed power of PV systems placed at rooftops was 18,60 MW_p. To estimate the REP, we'll search for research studies documenting the REP of solar parks in Crete Island. From J.Vourdoubas¹², it can be deduced that the average generation of a PV solar system of 1 MW, placed in a free-mounted situation and with optimal slope and Azimut, is 1.750 MWh. Assuming 20 % energy losses for rooftop installations, it can be considered that each MW of PV installed produces 1.400 MWh/year. Applying these assumptions over the installed PV power in 2019, we can obtain the figures of REP due to PV rooftop installations, in 2019, for Crete Island. It was 26.040 MWh. If we compare this figure with the one of the reference year of 2012 (from Figure 2-3) and we share the difference among the last 3 years (since the growth is concentrated in these years), we can obtain the rise of REP per year, which accounts for 4.903 MWh/year.

We can follow a similar procedure to determine the rise of REP per year in the pilot site of Girona province. Figure 2-4 shows the REP of the reference year for all the municipalities belonging to the pilot site of Girona province. Detailed consumption and source for each municipality are in Annex I. As can be seen, the total REP is 51.790,7 MWh. However, the high REP due to hydropower will be excluded from the REP evaluation since it is mainly due to high dams, which is out of the scope of the ePLANET project. Therefore, the baseline REP to be considered is the one related to PV installations, which is 163,7 MWh.

¹⁰ A. Gigantidou. 4th International Hybrid Power Systems Workshop. 'Out of the Blue Cypsis Elite Resort'. Agia Pelagia. Heraklion. Crete. Greece

¹¹ J. Vourdoubas. Use of Renewable Energy Sources for Energy Generation in Rural Areas in the Island of Crete, Greece. European Journal of Environmental and Earth Science. 30th november 2020. DOI :10.24018/ejgeo.2020.1.6.88. file:///Users/cipriano/Downloads/editor_in_chief,+EJGEO_88.pdf

¹² J. Vourdoubas. Use of Renewable Energy Sources for Energy Generation in Rural Areas in the Island of Crete, Greece. European Journal of Environmental and Earth Science. 30th november 2020. DOI :10.24018/ejgeo.2020.1.6.88. file:///Users/cipriano/Downloads/editor_in_chief,+EJGEO_88.pdf

Figure 2-4 Total REP from the Girona province pilot from the reference year of each municipality.

To assess the annual increase of REP due to PV installations, statistical data from the ICAEN can be found¹³. Figure 2-5 shows the evolution of PV self-consumption installations in the Girona province over the last few years. Although these are one of the typologies of PV installations, they will become the main target of the ePLANET actions, and, therefore, they will be considered as the basis for the EI-6. To determine the REP of the PV power of Figure 2-5, an average annual PV generation is provided by ICAEN. It is around 1370 MWh/year per 1 MW_p.

Figure 2-5. Evolution of the installed power (kW) of PV self-consumption installations in the Girona province

If we apply the average REP to the numbers in Figure 2-5, we can obtain the annual energy produced by PV self-consumption installation for each year. The following table shows a summary of this REP:

year	2019	2020	2021	2022
REP (MWh)	4.142,88	9.864	21.193,9	41.497,3

¹³<https://icaen.gencat.cat/ca/energia/autoconsum/Observatori-de-lautoconsum-a-catalunya/ranking/>

As can be seen, the rise of REP is almost exponential, and the initial baseline of 2012 is dramatically lower than the REP of the last years. Therefore, we'll determine the annual increase as the difference of REP of the previous 2 years, 2021 and 2022. This approximation gives the following figure for the pilot site of Girona province. The annual rise of REP is 20.303,4 MWh/year.

In the case of the pilot site in the Zlín region, there is no information from the SECAPs. Therefore, another data source is necessary to evaluate the existing REP in the region. EAZK proportionate a table of RES electricity generation (Table 2-20) with data from the electricity distribution companies.

Table 2-20 RES energy production in the Zlin region

Electricity production in MWh	Year 2001	Year 2014	Year 2021
Photovoltaics, Wind energy and water energy production	18.776	224.486	297.652

The main increase in production of RES generation increase was in years 2009 and 2010 due to high advantage feed-in tariff. This type of advantageous feed-in tariff was punctual and is unlikely that it happens again. For this is considered the energy production growth between 2014 and 2021. The average growth between the years 2014 and 2021 is 10.452,29 MWh/year.

It is expected that the ePLANET project will accelerate a 5% of the REP on the phase 1 regions: Girona province, Crete Island and Zlín region.

Table 2-21 Revised REP to be triggered by ePLANET in phase 1: involved pilot site regions

	REP increase	Percentage ePLANET	REP to be triggered by ePLANET
Girona province	20,303.40 MWh/year	5 %	1,015.17 MWh/year
Crete Island	4,903.00 MWh/year	5 %	245.15 MWh/year
Zlín region	10,452.29 MWh/year	5 %	522.61 MWh/year
TOTAL PHASE 1			2.601,03 MWh/year

2.7.2.2 Phase 2: Transferring and expansion

In phase 2, the involved use cases (UC1, UC2 and UC3) will address other follower regions from the open call of WP5 (7 already selected) and from the regions or municipalities which will sign the Memorandum of Adhesion within the upper level of the three involved pilot sites. Following the figures defined in the EI-1, the potential number of regions/municipalities to be engaged are:

- Upper level:
 - Catalonia: 6 regions/counties
 - Greece: 9 regions
 - Czech Republic: 10 areas/counties/association of municipalities
- Other EU regions:
 - Follower regions: 7

Only the percentage established in the GA is valid to assess the potential REP to be triggered within the project duration. It corresponds to 1% of the case of the municipalities/counties within the upper regional level and 2.5 % for the EU follower regions. A generic region with the same features as the Girona Province is considered a baseline to translate this percentage into specific figures. In this case, since there are only 3 more provinces equivalent to Girona

province in Catalonia, the concept of “region” will be translated to “county”. The Girona province is formed into 7 counties. Therefore, the generic county will have a baseline of REP equivalent to 1/7 of the figures of the Girona Province. In the case of Greece, Crete Island includes 4 regional units. The regional units have no administrative structure; however, as this was unknown when the GA was written, they are considered a group of municipalities to measure the Greek engagement. Therefore, the generic region will be equivalent to 1/4 of the baseline of Crete. In the case of the Czech Republic, since the Zlín region is formed by 10 “districts”, we’ll consider a generic “region/county/group of towns”, equivalent to 1/10 the figures of the Zlín Region. The following approach will be followed:

1. To use 1/4 of the REP of Crete Island, 1/7 of the Girona province and 1/10 REP of Zlín region as the baselines.
2. To estimate the REP at the upper level (Catalonia, Greece and the Czech Republic) by considering a 1 % of the baseline.
3. To estimate the REP of a European follower region by considering an average between the baseline of triggered REP of Girona province, Crete Island and Zlín region and by applying 2.5 % of this averaged baseline.
4. To evaluate the overall number of expected REP by considering 7 follower EU regions, 6 counties in Girona, 9 groups of municipalities in Greece, and 10 counties/association of municipalities in the Czech Republic.

Table 2-22 shows the results of the revised figures for this use case.

Table 2-22 Phase 2: REP to be triggered by ePLANET in the upper level and other EU regions

Reference county Girona province	2,900.49 MWh/year
Reference Region unit of Crete Island	1,225.75 MWh/year
Reference group of towns of Zlín region	1,045.23 MWh/year
Average	1,723.82 MWh/year
Catalonia	REP
REP to trigger	1 % reference county
	29.00 MWh/year
Number of counties within ePLANET	6 counties
REP to trigger in Catalonia	174.03 MWh/year
Greece	REP
REP to trigger	1 % reference region
	12.26 MWh/year
Number of regions within ePLANET	9 regions
REP to trigger in Greece	110.32 MWh/year
Czech Republic	REP
REP to trigger	1 % baseline
	10.45 MWh/year
Number of groups of towns within ePLANET	10 counties/groups of towns
REP to trigger in Czech Rep.	104.52 MWh/year
Other EU regions	REP
REP to trigger	2.5 % average
	43.10 MWh/year
Total EU follower regions	7 regions/counties
REP to trigger other EU regions	301.67 MWh/year

2.8 EI-7 Investments in sustainable energy triggered by the project

2.8.1 The hypotheses defined in the grant agreement

It's considered that the ePLANET project will clearly contribute to triggering and implementing renewable energy production in the participating regions. The trigger for the ePLANET project will be due, among others, to the improvement in governance and coordination between the different organizational levels of the public administration, favouring the exchange of information and experiences, favouring the aggregation of actions, and supporting public administrations in achieving a better financial and technical solution.

According to International Renewable Energy Agency (IRENA), the average implementation cost per MW of renewable installed capacity in 2019 was around 2 M€. Each MW of renewable power installed is estimated to produce 1.4 GWh of energy annually. So, according to the targets in EI-6 (Section 2.7), the EU should install enough power each year to generate 12.23 GWh more renewable energy than the previous year. So, it is estimated that it's needed 17.000 M€ to install all this power. ePLANET project aims to trigger directly and indirectly 0.5% of this volume, so it seeks to activate 85 M€.

2.8.2 Revision of the KPIs pilot site-by-pilot site basis

2.8.2.1 *Phase 1: Testing and pilot deployment*

In the use cases defined in ePLANET, two main investment categories are envisaged:

- Investments in Energy Efficiency Measures linked to the SECAPs (UC-1) and the energy management of public buildings (UC-2)
- Investments in Renewable Energy Production (UC-3 and UC-4)

Since there are no historical data on investments related to EEM, to evaluate the investments to be triggered by ePLANET, only the figures pertaining to investments in new REP will be considered. Therefore, we will assume the hypothesis of the GA where an investment of 2 M€ per 1.400 MWh is considered. Table 2-23 summarises the estimated investments for the 3 pilot sites.

Table 2-23 Revised Investments to be triggered by ePLANET in phase 1: involved pilot site regions

	REP to trigger by ePLANET	Investments (M€/year)	ePLANET (M€) (2 years)
Girona province	1,015.17 MWh/year	1.45 M€/year	2.90 M€
Crete Island	245.15 MWh/year	0.35 M€/year	0.70 M€
Zlín Region	522.61 MWh/year	0.75 M€/year	1.49 M€
	Total	2.55 M€	5.09 M€

2.8.2.2 *Phase 2: Transferring and expansion*

The same criteria to estimate the investments will be assumed in this phase. The REP figures will be obtained from Table 2-22. Table 2-24 shows the revised investments to be triggered in phase 2 of the ePLANET project.

Table 2-24 Revised Investments to be triggered by ePLANET in phase 2

	REP to trigger by ePLANET	Investments (M€/year)	ePLANET (M€) (2 years)
Catalonia	174.03 MWh/year	0.25 M€/year	0.50 M€
Greece	110.32 MWh/year	0.16 M€/year	0.32 M€
Czech Republic	104.52 MWh/year	0.15 M€/year	0.30 M€
EU follower regions	301.67 MWh/year	0.43 M€/year	0.86 M€
	Total	0.99 M€/year	1.97 M€

3 Summary of the revised KPIs of ePLANET

Table 3-1 summarises the revised KPIs of the ePLANET project. Each KPI is named Expected Impact (EI), as it is defined in the Grant Agreement, and numbered correspondingly.

Table 3-1. Summary of the revised KPIs of the ePLANET project

Impact Indic.	Description	Unit	Total	Phase 1- Pilot sites			Phase 2						
				Girona prov. 67 towns 2 counties	Crete Island 16 cities 2 reg. units	Zlín region 61 towns 2 assoc.	Catalonia 145 towns 6 counties	Greece 62 cities 9 regions	Czech Rep. 119 towns 10 assoc.	Other EU 101 cities 17 regions			
EI-1	Number of active stakeholders	Persons belonging to PPA	764										
EI-2	Number of institutionalized collaborations on ETM among PA	PPA with signed MoA	603	67 towns 1 county	16 cities 1 region	61 towns 1 assoc.	145 towns 14 counties	60 cities 6 regions	119 towns 7 assoc.	101 cities 12 regions			
EI-3	Number of PA and PO with improved skills in ET	Persons belonging to PPA	904	-----	-----	-----	402	172	330	-----			
EI-4	Number of policies influenced	Policies	32	-----	-----	-----	13	12	7	-----			
EI-5	FEC and CO ₂ -eq savings triggered	FEC GWh (2024) tCO ₂ -eq (2024) PEC GWh (2024)	129.01 74251.22 175.94	UC1 33.60 16581.3 46.71	UC1 30.67 16736.99 41.10	UC2 5% 5% 5%	UC2 5% 5% 5%	UC1 11.52 5685.02 16.01	UC1 13.80 7531.65 18.49	UC2 2.5% 2.5% 2.5%	UC2 2.5% 2.5% 2.5%	UC1 39.42 27716.27 53.63	UC2 1% 1% 1%
EI-6	REP triggered	GWh/year	2.47	1.02	0.25	0.52	0.17	0.11	0.10	0.30			
EI-7	Investments in sustainable energy triggered	million EUR	7.07	2.90	0.70	1.49	0.50	0.32	0.30	0.86			

4 ANNEX I: Baseline of FEC, CO₂-eq and REP in the municipalities of the pilot sites

4.1 Crete pilot

FEC and CO ₂ -eq emissions	REP															
<p data-bbox="327 600 743 667">Total final energy and CO₂ emissions in HERAKLION in 2011</p> <table border="1" data-bbox="244 678 818 992"> <thead> <tr> <th>Category</th> <th>Electricity</th> <th>Fossil fuels</th> <th>Non-energy related emissions</th> <th>Renewable fuels</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>FINAL ENERGY (MWh)</td> <td>290,253</td> <td>1,271,364</td> <td>0</td> <td>0</td> </tr> <tr> <td>EMISSIONS (tCO₂)</td> <td>366,589</td> <td>323,102</td> <td>0</td> <td>33,217</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Category	Electricity	Fossil fuels	Non-energy related emissions	Renewable fuels	FINAL ENERGY (MWh)	290,253	1,271,364	0	0	EMISSIONS (tCO ₂)	366,589	323,102	0	33,217	
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<p data-bbox="327 1037 743 1104">Total final energy and CO₂ emissions in HERSONISOS in 2011</p> <table border="1" data-bbox="244 1115 818 1429"> <thead> <tr> <th>Category</th> <th>Electricity</th> <th>Fossil fuels</th> <th>Non-energy related emissions</th> <th>Renewable fuels</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>FINAL ENERGY (MWh)</td> <td>105,199</td> <td>185,803</td> <td>0</td> <td>0</td> </tr> <tr> <td>EMISSIONS (tCO₂)</td> <td>79,635</td> <td>47,881</td> <td>0</td> <td>0</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	Category	Electricity	Fossil fuels	Non-energy related emissions	Renewable fuels	FINAL ENERGY (MWh)	105,199	185,803	0	0	EMISSIONS (tCO ₂)	79,635	47,881	0	0	
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EMISSIONS (tCO ₂)	50,323	60,276	0	0												

4.2 Girona pilot

